

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF BAMBOO, JUTE AND KENAF MAT-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Natural fibers, characterized by sustainability, have gained a considerable attention in recent years, due to their advantages of environmental acceptability and commercial viability. In this paper, several kinds of composites with natural fiber mat as reinforcement and unsaturated polyester (UP) as matrix, including Jute/UP, kenaf/UP and bamboo/UP, were fabricated by hand lay-up and compression molding methods. Their tensile properties were tested and discussed, as well as the low cycle fatigue (LCF) behaviour of three composites. After the test, the fracture cross sectional observations were carried out on the selected test specimens using a scanning electron microscope (SEM), with a focus on the fracture morphologies.

1 Introduction

Over the past few decades, there has been a growing interest in the use of natural fibers [1]. The applications of natural fibers in composite are also spreading widely in many sectors such as automobiles, furniture, packing construction and sports. This is mainly due to the advantages of natural fibers compared to synthetic fibers, i.e. low cost [2], low density, less damage to processing equipment [3], good relative mechanical properties, renewability, biodegradability [4]. Natural fibers were also introduced with the intention of yielding lighter composites, showing a trend to replace the existing glass fiber reinforced polymer composites [5]. One of the reasons for this phenomenon is that natural fibers have a comparable strength with glass fiber and a similar specific modulus [6]. Plant fibers is an important part of natural fiber, including bast (or stem, soft, or sclerenchyma) fibers, leaf or hard fibers, seed, fruit, wood, cereal straw, and other grass fibers. The most common natural plant used as reinforced fibers are bast fibers, such as hemp, jute, flax, kenaf, and sisal [7]. The worldwide availability of natural fibers and other abundantly accessible agro-waste is responsible for this new polymer science and engineering research. Since the development of the natural plant fibers reinforced composites is still in the primary stage, many research need to be done, especially the basic test such as the mechanical properties [8].

A recent study of the fiber content on mechanical properties of kenaf fiber reinforced composite was carried out by Nishino et al. He find that both Young's modulus and tensile strength increased with the increase of fiber content and showed the maximum values (Young's modulus; 6.4 GPa, and the tensile strength; 60 MPa) around a fiber content of 70 vol.% [9].

Liu et al. evaluated the effects of different fiber surface modifications, 2% NaOH, 2+5% NaOH (Note that 2+5% NaOH treatment is a continuation treatment from 2% NaOH process and then soaked with 5% NaOH) and coupling agent, on jute/polybutylene succinate bio-composites. The experiment results showed that surface modifications could remove surface impurities, increased surface roughness and reduced diameter of jute fiber, significantly increased the tensile strength and modulus of the composites but decreased breaking elongation [10].

V.M. Harik et al. conducted an experiment of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites subjected to axial tensile loading along longitudinal 0° orientation of fibers. They found that under high loads of low cycle fatigue (LCF), fatigue life of glass/epoxy composites is less than 10⁴ loading cycles due to the high property degradation rates that are noticeably higher than those during high-cycle fatigue (HCF) [11].

Similarly to other materials, natural fibers reinforced composites suffer physical or chemical degradation

and accumulate micromechanical damage in service [12], leading to catastrophic failure eventually, which is a major cause of material fracture. The full potential of composites as advanced materials can be realized only if the effect of long-term material properties can be properly understood and controlled. Deterioration of mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites might be severe when the composites are subjected to LCF [13]. LCF tests for the material were conducted generally under stress controlled cyclic loading. Enough attention has not been paid to the cyclic fatigue behavior of the material, yet [14], which is usually helpful when discussing the overall mechanical properties of composites. Therefore the LCF test was conducted in this paper in order to observe the tensile anti-fatigue property.

2 Fabrication of Composite

2.1 Materials

Because natural fibers are original short fibers, mat reinforcement form was focused in this paper. Besides, mats are characterized by simple manufacture process and lower cost. Information about the reinforcement and matrix is listed as follows:

2.1.1 Bamboo fiber mat

Bamboo fiber mat (bamboo fiber's density: 1.293g/cm^3 and the unit area weight of 907g/cm^2) is used.

2.1.2 Jute fiber mat

Jute fiber mat (punched mat from YANO SEIKEI Company, with an average density of 1.163g/cm^3 , and the unit area weight of 957g/cm^2) is used.

2.1.3 Kenaf fiber mat

Kenaf fiber mat (punched mat from PANASONIC Company, with an average density of 1.157g/cm^3 , and the unit area weight of the kenaf fiber mat of 542g/cm^2) is selected.

2.1.4 Unsaturated polyester

Unsaturated polyester resin (Showa: RIGORAC 150 HRBQNTNW, with a density of 1.25 and Young's modulus of 3.2GPa; Tensile strength 42MPa; elongation at break 2.18%) was used as matrix for natural fiber mats.

2.2 Fabrication and Specimens

The composites were fabricated by hand lay-up and followed by compression molding method. In order to obtain the similar fiber volume fraction for better comparison, thickness of the composites were controlled by spacers. After curing the resin at the room temperature for 24 hours, they were heated in an oven at 100°C for 2 hours as post cure.

The required size of specimens is shown by Figure.1. Total length is 200mm, while width is 20mm. There are Aluminum tabs covering both sides of two ends of the specimen by adhesion agent. Tabs are used to introduce load to the specimen, in case of the stress concentration and gripping damage, thus leading to an acceptable failure. And the details of size about the final specimens and taps were depicted and summarized in Figure.1&Table.1, including the fiber volume fraction.

Fig.1 Required size of specimens

Tab.1 Parameters of composites

Fiber mat/UP composite	V_f (%)	Average of Thickness (mm)	Average of Width (mm)
Bamboo	14.6	4.5	19.6
Jute	13.7	5.8	19.6
Kenaf	13.1	4.0	19.5

2.2 Experiments and conditions

Experiments in this paper consist of three parts, that is, tensile test, LCF tensile test and SEM.

In order to examine the tensile properties of Bamboo/UP, Jute/UP and Kenaf/UP, tensile test was conducted with WDW-20 at a test speed of 1 mm/min and at standard laboratory atmosphere (temperature: 23 ± 3 °C; relative humidity: $50 \pm 10\%$) according to ASTM D3039. The tested specimens were conditioned for 48 hours at room temperature. At least 3 pieces of specimens were repeated.

In the low cycle fatigue (LCF) evaluation, the cycle load was calculated and determined by the max value of load obtained from the quasi-static tensile test. Additionally, 30 cycles were performed when the stress arrived to pre-set load, which is 50%-55% of the corresponding max load. The stress-strain curve was recorded every 3 cycles, in order to see the trend of the tensile performance during the LCF test. And the tensile modulus was calculated every 3 cycles, too. After finishing the 30 cycles of LCF test, specimens were stretch to fracture. Then, the final curve of stress-strain after 30 cycles was also compared with that of non-cycle, to see if there was any change effected by the LCF test.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Tensile property

Typical tensile stress-strain curves of three kinds of natural fiber composites were shown in Figure 2. All of the tensile stresses were increased with the strain linearly until max values followed a sudden load down owing to the final and catastrophic fracture (Figure 2). It can be seen that natural fiber mat reinforced composite have similar tensile performance.

The detail tensile results of the natural fiber mat composites were summarized in Table 2&Figure.3. With respect to tensile modulus, kenaf /UP has got higher value than that of Bamboo mat/UP and Jute mat/UP. It can be seen from Table.2 that bamboo/UP and jute/UP have similar lower strength. Average tensile modulus of kenaf/UP is 5.52GPa, which is 35.1% higher than that of bamboo/UP, and 38.2% higher than that of jute/UP.

Referring to the tensile strength, kenaf mat composite seems stronger. While bamboo/UP and

jute/UP have similar lower strength. According to the Figure.3, it shows that the strength value of kenaf/UP is 27.88MPa, which is 24.7% higher than that of bamboo/UP, and 21.3% higher than that of jute/UP, respectively.

In the case of elongation at fracture, bamboo/UP and jute/UP have the similar value of 3.3% and 3.4%, respectively. While kenaf/UP gets the lowest elongation at fracture of 2.9%, which means that the kenaf/UP composites are more brittle.

It can be concluded that bamboo/UP and jute/UP have similar tensile property, while kanaf/UP seems to have both higher tensile modulus and strength, that is, kenaf/UP perhaps has better tensile property than jute/UP and bamboo/UP. When compared to the pure UP(tensile modulus:3.2GPa, strength 42MPa), natural fiber enhanced the tensile modulus as reinforcement but decreased the strength, which perhaps attributed to their poor interphase property between natural fibers and matrix.

Fig.2 Typical tensile stress-strain curves

Fig.3 Modulus and strength of three composites

Tab.2 Detail tensile results

Mat/UP composites	Average modulus (GPa)	Average strength (MPa)	Elongation at Fracture (%)	Knee point stress (MPa)
Bamboo/UP	4.1	22.4	3.3	3.5
Jute/UP	4.0	23.0	3.4	3.4
Kenaf/UP	5.5	27.9	2.9	2.8

3.2 Low cycle fatigue tensile property

As showing in Table.3, the pre-set load for the LCF test was made to be 50% -55% of the max load. And the pre-set load had exceeded the corresponding knee point, which shall cause unrecoverable fracture to the specimens. The stress-strain curves were recorded every three cycle, in order to see the trend of the tensile performance variation during the LCF test, including the tensile strength and modulus.

S-s curves of three composites during the LCF test are collected and shown in Figure.5.As an example, the max load value of jute/UP is 2640N, so the pre-set load for fatigue test was made to be 1450N.The stress-train curves in Figure.5(b) have shown no much difference during the LCF test. In additional, the final s-s curve is among all the curves, that is, the LCF tensile test didn't have a big effect on the bamboo/UP specimen.

Referring to the tensile modulus, Figure.6 shows that the tensile modulus summary during the LCF test by calculating every three times, including tensile modulus from the final stretch. And Figure.6 also revealing that the tensile modulus of jute/UP during the fatigue test is around 4.0 GPa, showing not much variation with a CV% value of 2.2%, either.

When it is regarding to the strength before and after the fatigue test, a typical stress-strain curve of non-cycled was chosen to compare with the final stress-

strain curve after 30 cycles LCF test. It can be seen from the Figure.7(a) that the tensile property of jute/UP hasn't changed much before and after the LCF test. In fact, the average strength before fatigue test is about 22.99MPa, while the value after test is 21.19MPa, decreasing slightly by 7.8%.

The details of the LCF tests were summarized in Tables.3&4, including the max load before the LCF test, and the pre-set load for fatigue test, modulus/strength before and after LCF test, as well as the change rate.Table.3 shows the change of modulus before and after the low cycle fatigue test. The low value of CV% under 2.5% suggests that modulus of three composites stay steady during the LCF test. And modulus have no big variation before and after the LCF test, as the changing rate remaining under 10%.Modulus during the LCF test of three composites was compared in Figure.&Table.4.It is revealing that kenaf/UP had the highest modulus while jute/UP the lowest, during the LCF test. As for strength, the LCF test of 30 cycles don't have a big effect on these three composites, either, according to the Table.4.Strength changing rate remains under 10%, which can be seen as no big difference, either.

All in all, the tensile property of these three natural fiber mat reinforced composites were hardly effected by the LCF test of 30 cycles, and seems to have good and stable anti-fatigue tensile property.

(a) Bamboo/UP

(b) Jute/UP

(c)Kenaf/UP

Fig.5 s-s curves of three composites during LCF test

Fig.6 Tensile modulus during LCF test

(a) Jute/UP

(b) Kenaf/UP

Fig.6 Comparison of s-s curves

Tab.4 Modulus before and after the LCF test

Average modulus	before test (GPa)	during test (GPa)	CV% during test (%)	Changing rate (%)
Bamboo/UP	4.1	4.4	2.4%	8.06%
Jute/UP	4.0	4.0	2.2%	0.24%
Kenaf/UP	5.5	5.3	2.1%	4.16%

Tab.3 Load and strength about the LCF test of three composite

Specimens	Load		Tensile Strength		
	Max load at the tensile test (N)	Pre-set load for LCF test (N)	Before LCF test (MPa)	After LCF test (MPa)	Changing rate (%)
Bamboo/UP	1989.0	1094.0 (55%)	22.4	21.9	↓2.1%
Jute/UP	2640.8	1452.4 (55%)	23.0	21.2	↓7.8%
Kenaf/UP	2212.3	1106.1 (50%)	27.9	28.9	↑3.7%

3.3 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

Cross sectional observations of molded sample before and after tensile test were carried out on the selected test specimens using a scanning electron microscope with a focus on the failure mechanism which occurred on the composites[15], including matrix fusion, state of resin impregnation, fiber/matrix interfacial interactions, fracture morphologies to characterize interfacial bonding and cohesion and their relationships to the test results. Gold was sputtered onto the specimens for electron conductivity before SEM observation.

The SEM micrographs for composite fracture were shown in Figure.8(a-d). In general, fibers are disorderly distributed in the matrix, and clear pull out, detachment and debonding of some of the reinforce fibers can be seen. In particular, large smooth zones are clearly evident, together with isolated broken fibers. In fact, the fracture mechanism, based on the morphology achieved, appears to involve both fiber pull-out and fiber breaking as well as macro-crack of matrix.

In the case of single fiber tensile properties showing in Table.5, single kenaf fiber gets the strength of

930MPa and modulus of 53 GPa[16], which is significant higher than bamboo and jute fiber. As a result, fiber breaking requires higher amounts of energy for kenaf fibers. Furthermore, Kenaf fibers have high characteristics compared to other natural fibers, i.e. longer fiber length, smaller diameter[17]. These shall be the reason that why kenaf/UP showed better tensile properties over bamboo/UP and jute/UP.

Besides the transverse fracture surface of broken fibers and macro-cracks, Figure.8(c) also show that there is clear long punched fibers in the fractural cross section of kenaf/UP, which is different from the other two composites. This can be seen to contribute to better adhesion of kenaf mat, thus resulting in higher strength. All of the above considerations can therefore account for the tensile strength of kenaf/UP composites being higher than that of bamboo/UP and jute/UP.

In summary, combining the SEM micrographs, it seems that the better tensile properties of Kenaf/UP can be attributed to better single fiber physical and tensile properties as well as good adhesive of mat as reinforcement.

Tab.5 Tensile properties of single fiber

Single fiber	Elongation (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)
bamboo	3.48	400–838	2.3–29.8
jute[18]	1.5–1.8	393–773	26.5
kenaf[19]	1.6	930	53

(a) Bamboo/UP

(b)Jute/UP

(c)Kenaf/UP

(d)Kenaf/UP after LCF test

Fig.8 SEM micrographs of composites after flexural failure:

4 Conclusions

Nowadays, natural fibers are applied into composite materials in the form of mat reinforcement. Bamboo mat, jute mat, kenaf mat were selected and used to fabricate composite with unsaturated polyester resin by hand lay-up and compression method.

In this paper, tensile property of three natural fibers mat reinforced composites were tested and analysed, including the tensile property of low-cycle fatigue test, as well as cross section observation by SEM.

The following points are drawn from the experimental results:

- (1) Bamboo/UP and jute/UP have similar tensile modulus and ultimate strength, while kenaf/UP have shown both higher tensile modulus and ultimate strength over the former two.
- (2) During the low-cycle fatigue test, the modulus of three composites didn't varied much. In the case of

the final stretch to fracture after 30 cycles of LCF test, the tensile modulus and strength didn't show much difference when comparing with the tensile results that of non-cycled specimens, respectively. It means the 30 cycles of LCF test have no significant effect on the tensile properties of these three composites.

(3) The SEM micrographs, combining with the single fiber tensile properties of bamboo, jute, kenaf, revealing that, the better tensile properties of kenaf/UP shall be attribute to better single fiber physical and tensile properties as well as higher interfacial adhesion to matrix.

Although there is a big gap compared with some synthetic fiber reinforce composite like glass-fiber mat reinforce composite, natural fibers mat reinforce composite show good tensile property as well as potential to replace the petroleum-based composite[20].

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